

Bayesian Information Fusion for State Estimation in AC/DC Networks with Unbalanced HVDC Grids

Vitor H. P. de Melo^{*‡§}, Marta Vanin^{*}, Hakan Ergun^{*‡}, João B. A. London Junior[§], and Dirk Van Hertem^{*‡}

^{*} KU Leuven, Dept. Electrical Engineering (ESAT) - Electa, Leuven, Belgium

[‡] Etch-EnergyVille, Thor Park 8310, Genk, Belgium

[§] University of São Paulo, Dept. of Electrical and Computing Engineering, São Carlos, Brazil

Abstract—This paper proposes a State Estimation (SE) method for AC/DC networks monitored through heterogeneous data sources, based on Bayesian Information Fusion (BIF). The proposed model allows to represent bipolar High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) grids operating in balanced or unbalanced mode. Unbalanced operation of bipolar HVDC grids is a natural consequence of single-pole outages, and may become a relevant operating condition in offshore grids, due to long repair times. This paper casts Forecasting-Aided State Estimation (FASE) as a generic constrained optimization problem, enabling the straightforward modeling of AC/DC converter operational limits through inequality constraints and the flexible adoption of different SE objectives. Both Weighted Least Squares (WLS) and Weighted Least Absolute Value (WLAV) objectives are employed. Results demonstrate that BIF leverages sparsely available data from synchronized measurements, providing reliable estimates in networks affected by intermittent renewable generation and actions of power electronic converters.

Index Terms—Bayesian Inference, HVDC, PMUs, State Estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

State Estimation (SE) is a vital tool for the safe operation of Electric Power Systems (EPS), as it provides reliable information on the (near) real-time system state [1]. Although SE is well established in transmission networks, conventional formulations must evolve to accommodate modern EPS characteristics, notably the increasing deployment of High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) technologies. These devices introduce new variables associated with power electronics-based converters and DC grid elements, and accurate monitoring of these quantities is essential to exploit the full potential of HVDC connections while maintaining system reliability.

This holds particularly true for Voltage Source Converter (VSC)-based HVDC systems, as they are expected to become the backbone of future multi-terminal, meshed DC grids for

large-scale renewable integration. The resulting complexity, combined with the stochastic nature of renewable generation, requires the development of SE formulations with advanced capabilities. For example, the fast control actions of VSCs may abruptly alter the grid state, motivating the development of SE applications that provide accurate tracking of such events.

The growing availability of phasor measurement units (PMUs) motivated the development of SE formulations for both AC and AC/DC systems that rely solely on high-reporting-rate synchrophasors, resulting in linear SE: [2]–[4] extended the linear SE formulation of [5] to AC/DC systems with LCC links in [2], [3] and VSC links in [4]. Recently, [6] proposed a linear Kalman filter SE for AC/DC microgrids using only synchronized measurements. Other works [2], [7] introduce nonlinear PMU-only formulations that include converter control information as part of the measurement model.

However, PMU deployment in transmission networks remains limited and often serves protection or monitoring purposes rather than SE. Moreover, most PMU-only studies assume that DC measurements can be synchronized through the PMU’s GPS signal, generalizing this idea with the term *Synchronized Measurement Units* (SMUs) [6]. While technically possible, such functionality is not available to scale, yet.

Therefore, synchronous PMU data must still be combined with asynchronous SCADA measurements to obtain adequate redundancy. Few studies address this hybrid scenario. Notably, [8]–[10] extend the traditional hybrid SE, which jointly processes SCADA and PMU data, via a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) estimator for AC/DC grids. Among these, [8], [9] model VSC-HVDC, while [10] focuses on LCC-HVDC. However, these all assume synchronized sampling, neglecting the inherent temporal misalignment between heterogeneous data sources. A two-stage approach in [11] partially addresses data heterogeneity, but does not explicitly handle the time desynchronization between SCADA and PMU.

This paper addresses this limitation by extending the Bayesian Information Fusion (BIF) framework of [12] for processing heterogeneous data in AC/DC systems. Measurements with slower reporting rates form the prior knowledge of the state variables, which is subsequently updated with high sampling rate SMUs to obtain posterior estimates. This hierarchical structure explicitly handles temporal misalignment and differing uncertainty levels across measurement types. Consequently, the proposed SE captures converter-driven events

Submitted to the 24th Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC 2026).
Corresponding author: vitorhpmelo@usp.br

Vitor H. P. de Melo and João B. A. London Junior are supported by São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP), grants nos. 2022/09203-0, 2023/17472-4 and 2024/21574-0; Marta Vanin, Hakan Ergun and Dirk Van Hertem are supported by the Horizon Europe project DC Protection, Security, Control and Optimisation (PROSECCO) - Grant Agreement: 101160687 and by the Flemish government by the project "Innovatieve oplossingen voor ondergrondse hoogspanningsleidingen en -netten" - Etch. The authors would like to thank Prof.

Frederik Geth from the University of Queensland, for his support during the implementations.

while preserving robustness to slower SCADA updates, even in systems that are not fully PMU-observable.

The BIF approach can be regarded as a Forecasting-Aided State Estimation (FASE) formulation. Inspired by [13], [14], we cast FASE as a generic constrained optimization problem solved via automatic differentiation tools. This modular formulation decouples the traditional SE objectives (e.g., WLS, WLAV) from the network constraints, allowing flexible experimentation and robust estimation. In this work, the Bayesian Information Fusion (BIF) approach was implemented using the traditional Weighted Least Squares (WLS) criterion, as in [12], and further extended to incorporate the robust Weighted Least Absolute Values (WLAV) formulation.

In this paper, the AC/DC SE in [14] is extended to incorporate PMU and converter station measurements in a FASE formulation that can integrate data with different time resolutions. The implementation supports multi-conductor HVDC modeling and can represent unbalanced bipolar operation. Although often neglected in SE literature, continuous unbalanced operation is emerging as an alternative to increase the availability of offshore installations, where cable repairs may take several months [15], [16]. Moreover, grid planning studies suggest that enabling mixed monopolar/bipolar configurations can reduce investment costs [15] without compromising reliability.

To summarize, this paper presents a *novel* FASE formulation for AC/DC networks with multi-conductor HVDC models, based on BIF. The proposed method achieves the following *contributions* to the state of the art of AC/DC SE:

- it enables to combine SCADA data and sparse SMU data, which are collected with different time resolutions, in a FASE fashion. This allows to improve estimation accuracy when variable renewable generation and fast converter control actions are present,
- the SE captures the physics of the unbalanced operation of DC bipoles, allowing to spot malfunctions and/or to capture advanced future HVDC grid operations,
- it combines the BIF structure with WLAV minimization, enhancing resilience against data temporal misalignment.

Moreover, by applying the proposed framework it was possible to derive the following analytical contributions:

- evaluating the impact of DC SMUs on SE performance. While often assumed available in PMU-based approaches, this data source is not yet standard, and most methods are not tested without it.
- Assessing whether including the converter operational limits (through inequality constraints) provides sufficient benefits to justify the extra computational cost stemming from their inclusion.

Being implemented as a generic optimization problem, the proposed framework enables an easy prototyping, comparison, and testing of alternative formulations, while facilitating the integration of complex constraints for AC/DC converters and multi-conductor grids. Such flexibility allows us to present extensive numerical results in this paper, to showcase the impact and performance of the aforementioned contributions.

TABLE I
NOTATION CONVENTIONS

<i>Generic quantities</i>		
Notation	Meaning	Example
Bold upper-case	Matrix	\mathbf{A}
Bold lower-case	Vector	\mathbf{x}
Calligraphic letter	Set	\mathcal{X}
Lower-case italic	Scalar quantity	x, a_{ij}, σ_i
Sans-serif letter	Generic network variable	x
Italic letter x	Generic state variable	x
Tilde accent	Forecasted value	\tilde{x}
Hat accent	Estimated value	\hat{x}
<i>Network-specific quantities</i>		
Notation	Meaning	
Upper-case italic	Network-specific variable	P, Q, U
Letter θ	Voltage angle variable	θ_i
Subscript i, j, e	Bus index	U_i, P_i
Subscript $l = (i, j)$	Branch index	P_l
Superscript dc	DC quantities	U_i^{dc}
Superscript cv	Converter quantities	P^{cv}
Dot	Complex quantity	\dot{U}_i
Operators \Re, \Im	Real / imaginary parts	$\Re\{\dot{U}_i\}, \Im\{\dot{U}_i\}$
Superscript ϕ	DC terminal	U_e^{dc}
Superscript p	Converter pole index	U_{filt}^{cv}

The data and code used in our experiments is made available open-source.¹

The notation in this paper follows two levels of abstraction. In Section II, statistical concepts from SE and BIF are described via **generic quantities**. Section III specifies these quantities for AC/DC networks, introducing **network-specific variables**. Table I summarizes the main notation used throughout the paper.

II. STATE ESTIMATION WITH BAYESIAN INFORMATION FUSION

SE processes a set of m measurements \mathcal{M} to estimate the most likely value of the set of network state variables \mathcal{X}_s ($n = |\mathcal{X}_s|$). Once \mathcal{X}_s components are determined, all other variables in the network space \mathcal{X} ($\mathcal{X}_s \subset \mathcal{X}$) can be obtained using the physical laws. Traditionally, \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{X}_s are correlated through the measurement model [1]:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{e}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{z} := [z_i]_{i \in \mathcal{M}}$ is the measurement vector, $\mathbf{x} := [x_i]_{i \in \mathcal{X}_s}$ is the state variables vector, $\mathbf{h} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is a function mapping \mathbf{x} to \mathbf{z} , and \mathbf{e} is the measurement's errors vector. Measurement errors are assumed independent and Gaussian with zero mean and standard deviation σ_i for all $i \in \mathcal{M}$.

The Weighted Least Squares (WLS) is the conventional SE method and finds \mathbf{x} by minimizing $J(\mathbf{x})$:

$$J(\mathbf{x}) = [\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})]^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} [\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})], \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}\{\sigma_1^2, \dots, \sigma_m^2\}$ is \mathbf{z} covariance matrix.

In Forecasting-Aided State Estimation (FASE), the components of Eq. (1) are expressed with respect to the time instant t

¹https://github.com/vitorhpmelo/ACDCStateEstimation/tree/PSSC2026_paper_results

$(\mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{e}_t)$ and complemented by a process model describing the state transition between consecutive time steps [17]:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{F}_t \mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \mathbf{v}_{t-1} + \mathbf{w}_t, \quad (3)$$

where, \mathbf{F}_t is the state transition matrix, \mathbf{v}_{t-1} is the trend vector, and \mathbf{w}_t is the process error, usually assumed to be Gaussian distributed [17], [18].

According to [18], FASE can be regarded as an extension of the WLS SE framework, wherein each new measurement sample \mathbf{z}_t is processed together with the *a priori* estimate of the state vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t$, obtained given the forecasting technique employed and the process model Eq. (3), to produce the estimated state vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t = \arg\min\{J(\mathbf{x}_t)\}$, via

$$J(\mathbf{x}_t) = [\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_t)]^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} [\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_t)] + [\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t - \mathbf{x}_t]^T \mathbf{A}^{-1} [\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t - \mathbf{x}_t] \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the forecasting error covariance matrix.

Inspired by [13], we reformulate FASE as generalized optimization problem, defined as:

$$\text{minimize: } \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \rho_m + \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{P}} \pi_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{subject to: } \mathbf{f}_1(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_2(\boldsymbol{\pi}, \mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{l}(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0. \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{x} := [x_i]_{i \in \mathcal{X}}$ ($\mathbf{x} \subset \mathbf{x}$) is the network variables vector, comprising all variables used in the SE problem. Eq. (5) minimizes the sum of the measurement residuals and the prior objectives, defined as function of the network variables in Eq.(6) and Eq.(7) respectively, whose detailed definitions are provided in Section II-A. Eq. (8) enforces network physical laws, e.g., Ohm's and Kirchhoff's equations, formulated as equality constraints, as is typically done in the context of optimal power flow (OPF). The corresponding equations are presented in Section III-A for the AC grid, Section III-B for the DC grid, and Section III-C for the converter stations. Measured quantities that are not part of the variable space of the Power Flow (PF) formulation \mathcal{X}_{pf} are described with Eq. (9), and are explained in Section III-D.

Eq. (10) enables the straightforward incorporation of inequality constraints and variable bounds, e.g., to model the limits of network components. In the case of HVDC converters, controls have built-in current, voltage, and power limits for protecting the power electronic devices from overloading, which can be used as supporting information by SE, as done in the case of VSC-based Flexible Alternating Current Transmission Systems (FACTS) devices in [19] and [20]. The proposed SE formulation is well-suited for including such constraints and for evaluating if the expected benefits justify the extra computational cost stemming from their inclusion.

A. Residuals definition

Eq. (5) consists of the sum of measurement residuals ρ_m and prior residuals π_{ij} , defined hereafter.

1) *Measurement Residuals*: are defined in the form $\rho := [\rho_m]$, Eq. (6), that can be written as a p-generic norm

$$\rho_m = \|z_m - x_m\|_p / \sigma_m^p, \quad (11)$$

where $x'_m \in \mathcal{X}$ is the network variable corresponding to measurement z_m . Different SE objectives can be used by varying p , e.g., $p = 1$ for WLAV and $p = 2$ for WLS.

To improve convergence with interior-point solvers, Eq. (11) is relaxed as:

$$\rho_m \geq (z_m - x_m)^p / \sigma_m^p; \rho_m \geq (x_m - z_m)^p / \sigma_m^p, \quad (12)$$

as proposed in [13], [14], with negligible impact on accuracy.

2) *Prior Residuals*: are defined by re-writing the second line in Eq. (4) as a summation. In this case, each prior residual π_{ij} in Eq. (7) corresponds to an ordered pair $(i, j) \in \mathcal{P}$:

$$\pi_{ij} = \frac{(\tilde{x}_i - x_i)(\tilde{x}_j - x_j)}{a_{ij}}, \quad (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}, \quad (13)$$

where a_{ij} is the (i, j) -th element of \mathbf{A} in Eq. (4), and

$$\mathcal{P} := \{(i, j) \mid a_{ij} \neq 0\}, \quad (14)$$

denotes the set of ordered index pairs corresponding to the nonzero entries of \mathbf{A} .

According to [18], FASE formulations differ mainly in the forecasting model used to compute $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathbf{A} , as well as in the choice of the set of forecasted variables.

B. Bayesian Information Fusion

The BIF approach decomposes the SE into a hierarchical model, partitioning the measurements into sampling layers (SL), which are disjoint subsets of \mathbf{z} , containing measurements with similar sampling rates. Measurements with low sampling rates are first used to form a prior estimate, which is then combined with faster, more accurate measurements to obtain the posterior estimate via Bayes' theorem.

Within this hierarchical procedure, each layer has its own measurement model and process model, connecting SL with the previous layer $SL - 1$:

$$\mathbf{z}_{SL} = \mathbf{h}_{SL}(\mathbf{x}_{SL}) + \mathbf{e}_{SL}, \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{SL} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{SL-1} + \mathbf{w}_{SL-1}, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{SL} is the state vector in the current SL , $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{SL-1}$ is the estimated state vector in the $SL - 1$ and \mathbf{w}_{SL-1} is a random component that describes the uncertainty between the time intervals of two sampling layers.

Similarly to FASE [17], a probabilistic model for \mathbf{x}_{SL} is introduced in Eq. (3). In this context, Bayesian inference can be employed by adopting a *prior* density $f_X(\mathbf{x}_{SL})$, induced by Eq. (16), and a *likelihood* $f_{Z|X}(\mathbf{z}_{SL} \mid \mathbf{x}_{SL})$, induced by Eq. (15). Then, Bayes' theorem gives the *posterior*:

$$f_{X|Z}(\mathbf{x}_{SL} \mid \mathbf{z}_{SL}) = \frac{f_{Z|X}(\mathbf{z}_{SL} \mid \mathbf{x}_{SL}) f_X(\mathbf{x}_{SL})}{f_Z(\mathbf{z}_{SL})}. \quad (17)$$

This posterior can be used to estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{SL}}$, via the *Maximum a Posteriori* (MAP) principle [12].

In the Bayesian context (Eq. (15))-Eq. (17)), the slower sampling layers (e.g., SCADA) are used to build a probabilistic prior over the system state, explicitly accounting for the possibility that the state vector may vary between consecutive samples of this same sampling layer. Faster, more accurate measurements (e.g., PMUs) are then combined with this prior, enabling tracking of these variations. In contrast, traditional hybrid approaches treat all measurements as if sampled simultaneously in a single \mathbf{z} vector, limiting the benefits of incorporating PMU data.

Since SE is a real-time application, it is desirable to adopt conjugate models, ensuring that the posterior distribution has a closed-form, thereby avoiding reliance on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods for posterior sampling, which are often associated with high computational cost and scalability issues [12], [21]. In this case, the MAP problem reduces to a standard optimization problem, which can be efficiently solved using traditional numerical methods within tractable computational times.

In this paper, a Gaussian Model is assumed, e.g.,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Prior : } \quad & \mathbf{x}_{\text{SL}} \sim N(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{SL}-1}, \mathbf{P}_{\text{SL}-1}) \\ \text{Likelihood : } & \mathbf{z}_{\text{SL}} | \mathbf{x}_{\text{SL}} \sim N(\mathbf{h}_{\text{SL}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{SL}}), \mathbf{R}_{\text{SL}}), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where \mathbf{R}_{SL} is SL measurement's covariance matrix, a sub-matrix of \mathbf{R} introduced in Eq. (2) corresponding only to SL measurements. $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{SL}-1}$ is estimated state using $SL-1$ sample, $\mathbf{P}_{\text{SL}-1}$ is the state covariance matrix, estimated as inverse of $SL-1$ Gain matrix:

$$\mathbf{G}_{\text{SL}-1}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{H}_{\text{SL}-1}(\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{R}_{\text{SL}-1}^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{\text{SL}-1}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{\text{SL}-1}(\mathbf{x}) = \partial \mathbf{h}_{\text{SL}-1}(\mathbf{x}) / \partial \mathbf{x}$, is $SL-1$ measurement Jacobian matrix.

As shown in [12] solving MAP using a Gaussian conjugated model is equivalent to minimizing (4), where $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{SL}-1}$ and $\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \mathbf{P}_{\text{SL}-1}^{-1}$. Thus it can be easily implemented via the generalized model described in eqs. (5)-(10).

Fig. 1 illustrates the hierarchical BIF procedure applied in this paper. The framework is well suited for modern grids, where synchronized PMU data provide fast, accurate measurements, but are insufficient to guarantee observability. Consequently, slower and unsynchronized SCADA measurements remain necessary to maintain system observability.

Within this structure, the SCADA measurements at sampling layer $SL-1$ are processed by a conventional state estimator (*SE*). The estimates are then used to calculate the prior distribution (Eqs. (18)-(19)). These quantities are subsequently embedded in the *FASE* formulation (Eqs. (4)-(10)), making $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{\text{SL}-1}$, $\mathbf{A}_i = \mathbf{G}_{\text{SL}-1}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{\text{SL}-1})$, and are then fused with the most recent sample of PMU measurements.

It is worth mentioning that, the approach is modular, i.e., *SE* can be any existing control-centers' estimator and only *FASE* and the *Prior* blocks needs to be added for PMU fusion. To ensure this modularity, $G_{\text{SL}-1}(x)$ is computed externally by automatic differentiation of *Enzyme.jl* [22]. This

Fig. 1. Bayesian Information Fusion Approach

procedure relies solely on the estimates provided by *SE* and on qualitative information about the measurements in $\mathbf{z}^{\text{SL}-1}$ (e.g., their type and location), without accessing or modifying the estimator's internal implementation.

III. AC/DC GRID MODELING

This section presents the AC/DC network model adopted in this work, which extends the OPF formulation from [15] for *FASE*. First, the Power Flow (PF) model is briefly described, showing its original variable space \mathcal{X}_{pf} (covering the AC and DC grids and converter stations). Subsequently, it is explained how \mathcal{X}_{pf} is expanded to include all measured quantities of interest, defining the *SE* variable space \mathcal{X}_{se} . Moreover, this section details the components of Eq. (8), which model the physical behavior of each network component.

A. AC grid model

The AC part of the network is modeled with the power-voltage formulation, with the voltages in polar coordinates (i.e., the so-called 'ACP' formulation). Thus, the AC variable space for the PF $\mathcal{X}_{\text{pf}}^{\text{ac}}$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{X}_{\text{pf}}^{\text{ac}} := \{U_i, \theta_i \mid i \in \mathcal{I}_{\text{ac}}\} \cup \{P_i, Q_i \mid i \in \mathcal{I}^{\text{ac}}\} \cup \{P_l, Q_l \mid l \in \mathcal{E}^{\text{ac}}\}, \quad (20)$$

where \mathcal{I}^{ac} is the set of AC buses and \mathcal{E}^{ac} is the set of directed AC branches², $\tilde{U}_i = U_i \angle \theta_i$ is bus i complex voltage, P_i (Q_i) is the active (reactive) power injection, and P_l (Q_l) the active (reactive) power flow in branch $l = (i, j)$ from i to j .

These variables are linked by a set of equality constraints defined in Eq. (8) of the *SE* model: P_l and Q_l are defined as functions of the nodal voltages (Ohm's Law), while the power balance at each node ensures that P_i and Q_i equal the sum of outgoing branch flows plus the contribution of shunt elements (capacitors or reactors), and AC/DC converters (Kirchhoff's Law). The full expressions for Kirchhoff's and Ohm's laws are quite standard and can be found in [23].

B. DC grid model

All equations for the DC network are presented w.r.t. the full bipole model, without loss of generality, since other configurations can be derived directly by omitting inactive

²Each branch between buses $\{i, j\}$ is represented in both directions, (i, j) and (j, i) .

terminals. Therefore, a bus e in the set of DC buses \mathcal{I}^{dc} is composed of three terminal voltages: neutral U_{e0}^{dc} , positive U_{e1}^{dc} , and negative U_{e2}^{dc} . Moreover, every DC branch has its currents in both directions modeled $I_{d0}^{dc}, I_{d1}^{dc}, I_{d2}^{dc}$.

The DC network variable space for the PF is defined by

$$\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{dc} = \{U_{e0}^{dc}, U_{e1}^{dc}, U_{e2}^{dc} \mid e \in \mathcal{I}^{dc}\} \cup \{I_{d0}^{dc}, I_{d1}^{dc}, I_{d2}^{dc} \mid d \in \mathcal{E}^{dc}\}. \quad (21)$$

These quantities are connected via Ohm's Law, following

$$I_{d\phi}^{dc} = (U_{e\phi}^{dc} - U_{f\phi}^{dc}) / r_{d\phi}, d = (e, f) \in \mathcal{E}^{dc} \quad (22)$$

where, $r_{d\phi}$ is the resistance of the branch connecting buses e and f in the terminal $\phi \in \{0, 1, 2\}$.

Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL) is enforced for each terminal ϕ of every DC bus. In Eq. (23) for $\phi \in \{1, 2\}$ and in Eq. (24) for $\phi = 0$

$$\sum_{cv \in \mathcal{C}_e} I_{\phi}^{cv,dc} + \sum_{d \in \mathcal{I}_{dc}^d} I_{d\phi}^{dc} = 0, \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{cv \in \mathcal{C}_e} I_0^{cv,dc} + \sum_{cv \in \mathcal{C}_e} I_g^{cv,dc} + \sum_{d \in \mathcal{I}_{dc}^d} I_{d0}^{dc} = 0, \quad (24)$$

where \mathcal{C}_e is the set of converters connected to bus e , \mathcal{E}_e^{dc} is the set of all directed branches starting from e . $I_{\phi}^{cv,dc}$ is the DC current injected by converter cv into terminal ϕ of bus e , and $I_g^{cv,dc}$ is the converter ground current at the neutral terminal.

C. AC/DC Converter station model

Fig. 2. Bipolar converter station (a) highlighting its AC variables (b) highlighting its DC variables.

Similarly to the DC grid, the converter stations are described with respect to the full bipole model, without loss of generality.

Readers are referred to [15], [23] for more details on modeling other converter configurations.

A full bipolar converter station $cv \in \mathcal{C}$ (Fig. 2) connects an AC bus $i \in \mathcal{I}^{ac}$ to a DC bus $e \in \mathcal{I}^{dc}$, and the variable space of a converter cv (\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv}) can be divided into two disjoint subsets: one for the AC variables $\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,ac}$, and other for the DC ones $\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,dc}$. The AC part comprises two radial subnetworks (one per pole $p \in \{1, 2\}$). Each one includes a transformer, a filter, a phase reactor, and an AC/DC power-electronic converter. For each pole p , two additional AC buses are introduced: the filter bus f^p and the AC/DC converter output bus o^p .

These two buses and the branches between them define the ac part of a converter cv variable space

$$\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,ac} = \{U_i^{cv}, \theta_i^{cv} \mid i \in \mathcal{I}^{cv,ac}\} \cup \{P_l^{cv}, Q_l^{cv}, \mid l \in \mathcal{E}^{cv,ac}\} \cup \{P_{o^p}^{cv}, Q_{o^p}^{cv}, I_{o^p}^{cv}, Q_{filt^p}^{cv} \mid p \in \{1, 2\}\}, \quad (25)$$

where $\mathcal{I}^{cv,ac}$ is the set of all ac internal buses of the converter cv , $\mathcal{E}^{cv,ac}$ is the set of all cv directed internal ac branches. $P_{o^p}^{cv}, Q_{o^p}^{cv}$ are active and reactive power injections in the AC/DC converter output bus, calculated as

$$P_{o^p}^{cv} + P_{o^p f^p}^{cv} = 0; Q_{o^p}^{cv} + Q_{o^p f^p}^{cv} = 0, \quad (26)$$

$I_{o^p}^{ac}$ is the magnitude of the AC current injected by the electronic converter, described by

$$(P_{o^p}^{cv})^2 + (Q_{o^p}^{cv})^2 = (U_{o^p}^{cv})^2 (I_{o^p}^{cv})^2. \quad (27)$$

The reactive power injected by the filter $Q_{filt^p}^{cv}$ is

$$Q_{filt^p}^{cv} = -b_{filt^p}^{cv} (U_{f^p}^{cv})^2. \quad (28)$$

Then the power balances in the filter buses are defined as

$$P_{f^p o^p}^{cv} + P_{f^p i}^{cv} = 0; Q_{f^p o^p}^{cv} + Q_{f^p i}^{cv} + Q_{filt^p}^{cv} = 0. \quad (29)$$

The power balance in the AC/DC converter connects $\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,ac}$ with $\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,dc}$, and is defined as

$$P_{o^p}^{cv} + P_p^{cv,dc} + P_{p0}^{cv,dc} = P_L^{cv}, \quad (30)$$

where P_L^{cv} is defined assuming a quadratic loss model

$$P_L^{cv} = a_p^{cv} + b_p^{cv} I_{o^p}^{ac} + c_p^{cv} (I_{o^p}^{ac})^2, \quad (31)$$

where, a_p^{cv} represents the no-load losses, b_p^{cv} represents the switching losses, c_p^{cv} represents the conduction losses. $P_p^{cv,dc}$ and $P_{p0}^{cv,dc}$ are calculated as

$$P_p^{cv,dc} = U_{e\phi}^{dc} I_p^{cv,dc}, \quad \forall (p, \phi) \in \{(1, 1), (2, 2)\}, \quad (32)$$

$$P_{p0}^{cv,dc} = U_{e0}^{dc} I_p^{cv,dc}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (33)$$

where $I_p^{cv,dc}$ is the DC current in each pole p , $I_{p0}^{cv,dc}$ is the current flowing from neutral to pole p , $U_{e\phi}^{dc}$ denotes the DC voltage magnitude at bus e and terminal ϕ . These quantities are connected through

$$I_p^{cv,dc} + I_{p0}^{cv,dc} = 0; I_0^{cv,dc} = I_{10}^{cv,dc} + I_{20}^{cv,dc}. \quad (34)$$

The grounding current of the converter is represented as

$$I_g^{cv,dc} = \frac{U_{e^0}^{dc}}{r_g^{cv}}, \quad (35)$$

where r_g^{cv} is the grounding resistance.

Thus $\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,dc}$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{X}_{pf}^{cv,dc} = \{P_p^{cv,dc}, P_{p^0}^{cv,dc}, I_p^{cv,dc}, I_{p^0}^{cv,dc}, |p \in \{1, 2\}\} \cup \{I_0^{cv,dc}, I_g^{cv,dc}\} \quad (36)$$

D. Mapping measured variables outside of the scope

1) *AC grid*: Only PMU currents are not mapped in \mathcal{X}_{pf} . These quantities can be mapped in rectangular form as

$$\Re\{\dot{I}_l\} = \frac{P_l \cos \theta_l + Q_l \sin \theta_l}{U_l}; \Im\{\dot{I}_l\} = \frac{P_l \sin \theta_l - Q_l \cos \theta_l}{U_l}, \quad (37)$$

where $\Re\{\dot{I}_l\}$ ($\Im\{\dot{I}_l\}$) is the real (imaginary) part of the complex current in the branch $l = (i, j)$ (\dot{I}_l). Current injections at bus i can be calculated by substituting the power flows with the injections in bus i .

2) *DC grid*: For the DC grid, only the power flows in the branches are not mapped, which can be calculated as

$$P_{ef\phi}^{dc} = U_{e\phi}^{dc} I_{ef\phi}^{dc} \quad (38)$$

where $P_{ef\phi}^{dc}$ is the power flow between buses e and f at terminal ϕ .

3) *Converter Station*: For the converter stations, the ratio between AC and DC voltage magnitudes is usually considered as a measurement, for a pole p of a converter cv as

$$M_p^{cv} = \frac{U_{e^k}^{dc} - U_{e^m}^{dc}}{U_{op}^{cv}} \quad (39)$$

where k and m denote the DC terminals of bus e where the pole p of cv is connected.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The simulations were performed on two different AC/DC test systems: the first one, named ‘‘case 5’’ [15], is the modified version of the original case 5 of [24], which contains an unbalanced multi-terminal DC grid, shown in Fig. 3 (a) together with the measurement set employed in the paper; and (b) the second test system is a modified version of the IEEE 118 bus test case from [25], which incorporates an HVDC multi-terminal bipolar grid, named ‘‘case 118’’ in this paper.

In the tests, SMUs provide time-synchronized measurements for the AC side (via PMUs), and the benefits of synchronized DC measurements are also evaluated. Unsynchronized measurements are assumed to be transmitted through the SCADA system. The corresponding measured variables are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Two methods for performing SE with heterogeneous data sources are evaluated. The BIF approach described in Section II-B (abbreviated as ‘‘Bay’’ in this section) and the traditional hybrid approach [10] that processes all measurements together in the same vector \mathbf{z} , (abbreviated ‘‘Hyb’’ in this section). The paper also reports results for the BIF prior

Fig. 3. Test systems with measurement set. In (a) Case 5, with an unbalanced HVDC grid from [15] (b) Case 118: [25] version of IEEE 118 bus system, evidencing the HVDC grid part.

(abbreviated ‘‘Prior’’ in this section), to evaluate the accuracy of the SE without SMUs. Each method is evaluated using the WLS and WLAV measurement residual definitions.

The reference value for the network variables at a time instant t is obtained via PF simulations. Then, to emulate real-world conditions, noise was added to the measured values as

$$z_{m,t} = z_{m,t}^{pf} + \eta \sigma_{m,t}; \sigma_{m,t} = \frac{|z_{m,t}^{pf}| pr_m}{3}, \quad (40)$$

where $z_{m,t}$ is the measurement m in instant t , $z_{m,t}^{pf}$ the PF output, $\eta \sim N(0,1)$ and pr_m is a parameter to m meter’s precision (2% for SCADA and 0.1% for SMU). In the tests, the SMU data arrives once every 100 ms, while SCADA data is updated every 2 s.

Monte Carlo simulations were repeated $n_{sim} = 100$ times over the entire interval (from $t = 0$ to $t = T$). The ‘‘Bay’’ and ‘‘Hyb’’ provide results at each SMU sample, combining it with the most recent SCADA sample. To guarantee a fair comparison, for each sample n at time t , both methods used the same noisy measurement set. In the Hyb, SCADA data is included with SMU measurements in the \mathbf{z} vector, while in the Bay, it is incorporated through the prior, as shown in Fig. 1.

In the tests, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is used to

evaluate accuracy:

$$MAE_{\mathcal{L}} = \frac{1}{n_{\text{sim}}T|\mathcal{L}|} \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\text{sim}}} \sum_{i=0}^T \sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} \left| \hat{x}_{i,t}^k - x_{i,t}^{pf} \right|, \quad (41)$$

where $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is the set of network variables for which MAE is computed, $\hat{x}_{i,t}^k$ is the variable estimated value in the simulation k in time instant t , and $x_{i,t}^{pf}$ its value in the PF.

A. Effect of DC Synchronized Measurements

In this test, “case 5” is assumed to be in a fully stationary condition (and $T = 1$), i.e., there are no variations in the values of loads, generator outputs, or electronic converter setpoints. Table II presents the MAE calculated for the bus voltages in each part of the grid, comparing the performance of each method, using the WLS and WLAV residual definitions.

This scenario emulates an ideal condition in which all measurements correspond to the same operational state of the system. This is a best-case scenario for the “Hyb” approach, as it processes all measurements in a single \mathbf{z} . Even so, when comparing the total MAE, the “Bay” approach outperforms it. Similar results have been obtained with BIF in [12], which can be attributed to the superior ability of these methods to handle information with highly distinct variances.

TABLE II
MAE CONSIDERING DIFFERENT RESIDUAL DEFINITIONS ACROSS NETWORK PARTS

Grid Part	WLS			WLAV		
	Prior	Bay	Hyb	Prior	Bay	Hyb
AC	6.51e-4	1.29e-4	2.63e-4	7.28e-4	1.39e-4	1.32e-4
DC	7.59e-4	7.15e-4	7.28e-4	8.45e-4	8.11e-4	8.66e-4
Conv	6.32e-4	1.24e-4	2.43e-4	7.12e-4	1.29e-4	1.27e-4
Total	6.81e-4	3.22e-4	4.11e-4	7.62e-4	3.60e-4	3.75e-4

For the AC grid and the converter variables, Hyb and Bay present considerable improvements with respect to Prior, but the same does not happen for the DC grid. To further investigate why, Fig. 4 shows the MAE per bus, using the WLS, in two cases for stationary condition: without DC SMUs (as in Tab. II) and introducing synchronized voltage measurements in DC buses 1 and 2. To complement, Table III shows the MAE for the bus voltages in each part of the grid, for WLAV residual definition with and without SMUs.

Fig. 4. Per-bus MAE for Case 5 in the stationary condition, using the rWLS residual definition, per component, without DC SMUs and with DC SMUs.

AC Area 1 (buses 1–5) in Fig. 3 is fully observable with PMUs, whereas in Area 2 (buses 6–10) only two phasor measurements are available. Although Area 1 buses present lower MAE for Hyb and Bay, all buses (areas 1 and 2) present lower MAE compared to Prior, showing how PMUs, even if sparsely available, can improve SE substantially. Such behavior arises because AC variables are strongly interconnected through the remaining measurements and constraints forming the measurement model and process model (initially described in Eq. (1) and Eq. (3) and implicit in Eqs. (5)–(10)), allowing the influence of sparsely deployed high-accuracy data to propagate across the network. This effect also extends to converter internal AC networks, which exhibit lower MAEs for Hyb and Bay despite lacking PMU monitoring.

TABLE III
MAE CONSIDERING THE WLAV RESIDUAL DEFINITION FOR EACH NETWORK PART, WITH DC VOLTAGE SMU AND WITHOUT DC SMUS

Grid Part	No DC SMUs			With DC SMUs		
	AC	DC	Conv	AC	DC	Conv
Bay	1.39e-4	8.11e-4	1.29e-4	1.41e-4	1.61e-4	1.44e-4
Hyb	1.32e-4	8.66e-4	1.27e-4	1.33e-4	1.60e-4	1.28e-4

However, AC SMUs does not improve the estimate of DC grid variables. Only when DC SMUs are introduced do Bay and Hyb show improvements compared to Prior, as seen in Tab. III and Fig 4. In the tests, just two DC SMUs were sufficient to enhance accuracy for all DC variables. Moreover, the introduction of DC SMUs do not improve the accuracy of AC network variables. This happens because the coupling between areas is weak. Note that, for each converter, only the losses constraints (eq. (30)) and the M measurements (eq. (39)) connect AC and DC variable spaces.

B. Effect of Smooth Variations and Sudden Changes

This test evaluates the performance of the methods in a non-stationary scenario for “case 118”. Thus, the loads are subjected to small fluctuations over time, following

$$P_{i,t} \sim N(P_{i,t-1}, \sigma_{P_{i,t}}); Q_{i,t} \sim N(Q_{i,t-1}, \sigma_{Q_{i,t}}) \quad (42)$$

where $P_{i,t}$ ($Q_{i,t}$) is the active (reactive) injection in bus i at t , $P_{i,t-1}$ and $Q_{i,t-1}$ their values in the previous time stamp. To guarantee that these variations are small, very low standard deviations are chosen: $\sigma_{P_{i,t}} = |P_{i,t-1}|/200$ and $\sigma_{Q_{i,t}} = |Q_{i,t-1}|/200$. In addition, the active power provided by the generators connected to the DC grid (buses 119 to 123) also suffered fluctuations following Eq. (42), emulating stochastic behavior of wind generation, with $\sigma_{P_{i,t}} = |P_{i,t-1}|/100$.

Moreover, 5% of loads were randomly chosen to undergo sudden changes, using the values of Tab. IV. Furthermore, voltages of buses 6 and 8 are increased by 1% at $t=2.5s$ and $t=4.5s$, respectively.

Tab. V shows the MAE obtained for the entire simulation ($T=5s$, with 0.1s time steps). In this test, Bay outperforms Hyb across all network parts, with a larger margin than in Section IV-A. The best performance is obtained with WLS.

TABLE IV
LOADS OF CASE 118 SUBJECTED TO SUDDEN CHANGES

Bus	12	15	57	76	102	106
t	3.1	2.0	2.6	3.2	3.1	1.2
Variation (%)	-9.72	-8.02	-29.38	-6.36	3.17	16.37

TABLE V
MAE FOR THE ENTIRE SIMULATION ACCORDING TO THE VOLTAGES IN THE NETWORK BUSES

Method	WLS			WLAV		
	AC	DC	Conv	AC	DC	Conv
Hyb	3.3e-4	3.3e-4	4.3e-4	2.3e-4	3.2e-4	4.4e-4
Bay	2.1e-4	1.8e-4	2.8e-4	2.1e-4	1.9e-4	3.6e-4

Fig. 5 shows the MAE for bus voltages in each part of the grid over time. For the AC and converter variables, the most prominent peaks occur at $t = 2.5s$ and $t = 4.5s$ for the Hyb method, which correspond to converter setpoint changes. This temporarily renders SCADA data inconsistent with the updated system state, impacting Hyb more strongly because it processes all measurements simultaneously in a single \mathbf{z} vector and cannot fully exploit the more recent SMU information. Still, both Hyb and BIF achieve full recovery from the event only upon receipt of the next SCADA sample, e.g., $t = 4 s$.

In the Hyb method, WLAV presented more robustness to data inconsistencies, achieving considerably lower MAEs for the AC grid than Hyb-WLS while maintaining comparable accuracy for converter and DC quantities (Tab. V, Fig. 5). However, its performance depends on PMU redundancy: in Fig. 3(b), bus 6 has only one incident current PMU, while bus 8 has two; consequently, a sudden change at bus 6 affects WLAV more strongly.

A similar effect occurs in the DC grid, where only three DC SMUs are sparsely deployed. Small generator variations make SCADA data inconsistent, such that Bay is more stable.

C. Effect of Converter Constraints

This test assesses the effect of adding converter limits as inequality constraints in Eq. (10), by varying the active power limit of the converter connected to bus 11 in “case 5”, considering the stationary case of Section IV-A. The active power through this converter is 0.436 p.u. in the PF solution

and the estimator is tested with five limits: 0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.5 and 0.42 p.u. The last limit (0.42 p.u.) lies below the actual flow (3.8% lower), emulating a slightly overloaded device.

Fig. 6. (a) MAE for all bus voltages in Case 5 (stationary) with different active-power limits for the converter at bus 11. (b) Estimated value for the converter at bus 11 active power with different limits for this variable.

Fig 6 (a) shows MAE calculated for all network bus voltages, with only the Bay method (similar behaviors are observed by Hyb and Prior), using WLS and WLAV. As expected, when the limit is below the reference value for the variable (from the PF), the MAE for all network rises, as the estimator cannot represent the actual operational state under this condition. Fig. 6 (b) shows all Monte Carlo estimates of this converter active power. When the limit is enforced at 0.42 p.u., the estimates become biased toward the bound, and overloads are masked in the SE results.

With a 0.5 p.u. bound, WLS yields a slightly higher MAE than values above it, indicating residual bias due to an active constraint. Thus, SE limits should be set above the true equipment limits to avoid bias and prevent masking of overloads.

D. Computational Aspects

The tests were carried out on a computer with an Intel i7-14900 processor and 64 Gb of RAM, with JULIA 1.11.5, IPOPT 1.7.2, ENZYME 0.13.61. Tab. VI provides the Ipopt execution time for each of the methods, with WLS and WLAV, in the stationary case.

It is worth mentioning that the implementation presented in this paper is not intended for real-time operation, but rather to enable flexible prototyping of FASE formulations. As a drawback, this approach increases the number of state variables and, consequently, the computational cost. Nevertheless, the observed execution times provide useful insight into the relative complexity of the different methods.

TABLE VI
IPOPT EXECUTION TIMES FOR EACH METHOD, WITH BOTH MEASUREMENT RESIDUAL DEFINITIONS

Obj	Case5			Case118		
	Prior	Bay	Hyb	Prior	Bay	Hyb
WLS	0.29s	0.15s	0.32s	0.98s	0.74s	1.79s
WLAV	0.08s	0.10s	0.08s	0.85s	2.23s	1.15s

For the WLS residual, the Bay method is faster because the squared-error norm is consistent with a Gaussian-conjugate model with the Gaussian prior. The WLAV, however, corresponds to the Laplacian error model, and although it can be

Fig. 5. MAE for the bus voltages in each network part, for the simulation with load variation and sudden changes.

seen as a special case of the Generalized Gaussian distribution, the discrepancy between objectives seems to slow down convergence. Moreover, the Gaussian-conjugate model can be implemented within traditional Gauss-Newton solvers [12] for SE, yielding much lower computational times, while the same approach cannot be directly applied to WLAV. Still, interior-point algorithms specialized for SE, similar to in [20], could be explored to reduce computational costs.

The computation times for $G_{SL-1}(\mathbf{x})$ (Eq. (19)) using ENZYME were

- Case 5: 6 ms
- Case 118: 321 ms

Although these times can be significantly reduced by explicitly computing the measurement Jacobian, as in conventional SE methods [12], they remain acceptable within typical SCADA sampling intervals.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper frames FASE as an optimization problem, providing a flexible platform for prototyping formulations while easing the modeling of HVDC components. This framework is combined with Bayesian Information Fusion to devise an estimator that adequately integrates heterogeneous measurement sources. The proposed formulation delivers more accurate estimates for networks with volatile behavior driven by electronic converters and renewable generation.

Numerical results compare the BIF approach with the conventional hybrid methods (Hyb), applying both WLS and WLAV residual minimization. The BIF consistently extracts more value from sparsely available SMUs and outperforms Hyb under temporal misalignment and converter-driven fast changes. Combining BIF with a WLAV objective further increases robustness to inconsistent data, whereas the WLS variant remains computationally attractive due to its compatibility with Gauss-Newton solvers. Results also indicate that PMU-driven gains are mostly confined to the AC side under weak AC/DC coupling; hence, DC SMUs are required to improve HVDC observability and SE reliability.

Future studies will focus on improving prior models, using physics-informed, or regime-switching priors. They will also investigate the coupling of the AC/DC problem from an observability perspective, examining how additional measurements and constraints can be included to enhance interactions between DC and AC estimates. Finally, computationally efficient BIF-WLAV formulations will be explored.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bretas, N. G. Bretas, J. B. A. J. London, and B. E. B. Carvalho, *Cyber-Physical Power Systems State Estimation*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 2021, 1st edition.
- [2] W. Li and L. Vanfretti, "Inclusion of classic hvdc links in a pmu-based state estimator," in *2014 IEEE PES General Meeting*, 2014, pp. 1–5.
- [3] O. Darmis, G. Karvelis, and G. N. Korres, "PMU-Based State Estimation for Networks Containing LCC-HVDC Links," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2475–2478, 2022.
- [4] G. I. Karvelis and G. N. Korres, "Pmu-based state estimator for power systems including vsc-hvdc links," *Proc. IEEE GPECOM 2022*, 2022.
- [5] A. G. Phadke, J. S. Thorp, and K. Karimi, "State estimation with phasor measurements," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 233–238, 2007.
- [6] W. Lambrichts and M. Paolone, "Linear Recursive State Estimation of Hybrid and Unbalanced AC/DC Micro-Grids Using Synchronized Measurements," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 54–67, 2023.
- [7] W. Li, L. Vanfretti, and J. H. Chow, "Pseudo-dynamic network modeling for pmu-based state estimation of hybrid ac/dc grids," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 4006–4016, 2017.
- [8] E. Zamora-Cárdenas, C. Fuerte-Esquivel, A. Pizano-Martinez, and H. Estrada-García, "Hybrid state estimator considering scada and synchronized phasor measurements in vsc-hvdc transmission links," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 133, pp. 42–50, 2016.
- [9] R. Martínez-Parrales and C. R. Fuerte-Esquivel, "A new unified approach for the state estimation and bad data analysis of electric power transmission systems with multi-terminal VSC-based HVDC networks," *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 160, pp. 251–260, 2018.
- [10] G. I. Karvelis, G. N. Korres, and O. A. Darmis, "State Estimation Using SCADA and PMU Measurements for Networks Containing Classic HVDC Links," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 212, 2022.
- [11] A. A. Aljabrine, A. A. Smadi, Y. Chakhchoukh, B. K. Johnson, and H. Lei, "Resiliency improvement of an ac/dc power grid with embedded lcc-hvdc using robust power system state estimation," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 23, p. 7847, 2021.
- [12] J. A. D. Massignan *et al.*, "Bayesian inference approach for information fusion in distribution system state estimation," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 526–540, 2022.
- [13] M. Vanin, T. Van Acker, R. D'hulst, and D. Van Hertem, "A framework for constrained static state estimation in unbalanced distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2075–2085, 2022.
- [14] M. Vanin, H. Ergun, and D. Van Hertem, "State estimation in unbalanced ac/dc networks," in *Proc. 22nd IET Int. Conf. AC & DC Power Transm.*, 2025, pp. 120–124.
- [15] C. K. Jat, J. Dave, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "Hybrid ac/dc opf model for unbalanced operation of bipolar hvdc grids," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 4987–4997, 2024.
- [16] L. Guo *et al.*, "Nodal reliability evaluation for a vsc-mtdc-based hybrid ac/dc power system," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 2300–2312, 2019.
- [17] J. Zhao *et al.*, "Power system dynamic state estimation: Motivations, definitions, methodologies, and future work," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 3188–3198, 2019.
- [18] M. B. Do Coutto Filho and J. C. Stacchini de Souza, "Forecasting-aided state estimation—part i: Panorama," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 1667–1677, 2009.
- [19] B. Xu and A. Abur, "State estimation of systems with upfcs using the interior point method," *IEEE Trans. on Power Sys.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1635–1641, 2004.
- [20] C. Rakpenthai *et al.*, "Power system with multi-type facts devices states estimation based on predictor-corrector interior point algorithm," *IJEPES*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 160–166, 2009.
- [21] J. A. Massignan, J. B. London, C. D. Maciel, M. Bessani, and V. Miranda, "Pmus and scada measurements in power system state estimation through bayesian inference," in *2019 IEEE Milan PowerTech*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [22] W. Moses and V. Churavy, "Instead of rewriting foreign code for machine learning, automatically synthesize fast gradients," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 33, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2020.
- [23] H. Ergun, J. Dave, D. Van Hertem, and F. Geth, "Optimal power flow for ac–dc grids: Formulation, convex relaxation, linear approximation, and implementation," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 2980–2990, 2019.
- [24] R. D. Zimmerman, C. E. Murillo-Sánchez, and R. J. Thomas, "Matpower: Steady-state operations, planning, and analysis tools for power systems research and education," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 12–19, 2011.
- [25] J. Cao, W. Du, and H. F. Wang, "An improved corrective security constrained opf for meshed ac/dc grids with multi-terminal vsc-hvdc," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 485–495, 2016.